

Measuring apparatus · Creep · Temperature · Nylon6.6 yarn and cords

A high temperature creep measuring apparatus capable of operating at different stress levels over a wide range of temperatures and humidities was built. The apparatus was used to investigate creep behaviour of nylon6.6 tyre cords, under isothermal and non-isothermal (cyclic) operating modes. Under both operating conditions, cords exhibited instantaneous extensions on loading followed by steady creep over time with an eventual failure. Increasing operating temperature accelerated creep rate and reduced creep failure time. At non-isothermal operating temperatures, the cords exhibited approximately 5–7 times longer creep lives than at steady state isothermal operating temperatures.

Kriechen von Reifencord aus Nylon 6,6 bei hohen Temperaturen

Kriechen · Temperatur · Garne und Cord · Nylon 6,6 · Messapparatur

Eine Apparatur zur Messung des Kriechens von Cord in einem breiten Bereich hoher Temperaturen und definierter Luftfeuchte wurde entwickelt. Diese Apparatur wurde zur Untersuchung des Kriechverhaltens von Reifencord aus Nylon 6,6 unter isothermen und nichtisothermen Bedingungen eingesetzt. In beiden Fällen wurde nach einer kurzen Dehnphase der zeitabhängige Kriechvorgang beobachtet. Durch die Temperaturerhöhung wurde eine Beschleunigung der Kriechgeschwindigkeit und eine verminderte Zeit in der Versagen auftritt registriert. Unter nichtisothermen Bedingungen zeigten die Corde eine 5–7 mal längere Kriechzeit als unter stationären Bedingungen.

High Temperature Creep Performance of Nylon 6.6 Tyre Cords

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High tenacity nylon6.6 filaments exhibit superior strength, high toughness and excellent elongation-recovery relationships. These properties of nylon6.6 fibres are successfully used in many industrial applications including tyre cords, conveyor belts, ropes etc. Strong and tough nylon6.6 cords are popular for the tyres, which are normally used for aircraft, heavy trucks, coaches etc. The high strength of nylon6.6 cord provides a reinforcing power to the carcass, while high elastic recovery and toughness provide the flexibility and structural integrity required at the side walls of the tyre under severe conditions.

Most of the thermoplastic fibres such as nylon6.6, nylon6, polyester, etc show significant changes in mechanical performance when they are subjected to high temperatures and temperature variations [1]. The flexible aliphatic structure of nylon filaments offers excellent elongation-recovery relationships. Leaderman's [2] experiments on creep of nylon filaments revealed that even when the filaments were stressed and taken close to rupture at standard conditions of temperature and humidity, they recovered almost completely to their unstretched length soon after the stress was removed. But Takeyama and Mastui [3] observed that at high temperatures, a high level of stress imposed on filaments produces a continuous and rapid creep deformation leading to the occurrence of fracture and ultimate failure. Today, technological developments and better understanding of structure-property relationships of fibres enable us to produce a nylon6.6 tyre cord that has very high creep and fatigue lives. Nevertheless, the creep behaviour of high tenacity nylon6.6 cords used for tyres and other applications at high operating temperatures

and at varied relative humidity is poorly understood. Lack of availability of high temperature creep measuring apparatus had always been a problem in developing a better understanding of fibre's creep behaviour.

This paper reports on the development of a new high temperature creep measuring apparatus, and preliminary creep results obtained on nylon6.6 tyre materials, involving certain process and material variables.

A new creep measuring apparatus

The creep measuring apparatus consists of an experimental chamber and a treatment chamber as shown in Fig. 1. The treatment and experimental areas are well insulated to minimise the loss of heat to the outside. The inside dimensions of the experimental chamber are 40 cm × 40 cm × 45 cm which permits testing of a 20 cm specimen and allows the specimen to extend and creep until it ruptures. The apparatus is made of a 1 mm thick inside wall from stainless steel which does not degrade due to temperature or humidity, and a 2.5 mm wall from ordinary steel painted to prevent rusting. Air circulates between the two walls 80 mm apart for insulation. In the treatment area, air is treated to suit the required conditions and circulated with the help of a fan. Experimental temperatures (up to 200 °C) can be held either constant or controlled in cyclic modes by means of adjustable contact thermometers, which through a number of relays ensure that the correct conditions are produced.

Cooling is achieved by using a refrigeration compressor. Humidity in the working chamber can be altered by using

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the newly built creep measuring apparatus

a water vapour injector. The supplies of heat, cold air, and water vapour are controlled through relays which open and close at appropriate controlled times. To enhance the method of control, energy regulators are used in heater and water vapour injector circuits, which reduce the possibility of unwanted fluctuations of temperature and humidity to a minimum. Experiments on effect of humidity on the creep of nylon6.6 tyre cords are not reported in this paper.

Creep behaviour of yarn or cord specimens is measured with the help of a linear variable differential transducer (LVDT) situated under the treatment chamber so that it is not affected by temperature and humidity changes. The temperature and humidity are measured using a thermocouple and hygrometer respectively. Information relating to temperature, humidity and creep performance of the specimen at any given time during the experiment can be read, stored and displayed on a linked computer. The time at which the specimen ruptures is measured using a time counter. The time counter is connected to an electronic switch, which stops as soon as the specimen breaks. The basic environmental chamber design of the creep measuring apparatus was adapted from the WEYCO climatic cabinet developed by Fisons [4].

Experimental materials

All experimental materials were either nylon6.6 filament yarns or cords made from them. The samples were obtained from Du Pont Nylon U. K. The yarn was type 728 with a linear density of 140 tex. The yarns were converted into cords and subsequently dipped with RFL (resorcinol – formaldehyde – latex) dope. The physical properties of the samples of yarn, converted untreated cord (raw cord) and cord dipped in RFL referred to as dipped cord, were measured at standard atmospheric conditions of 65 % relative humidity and 21 °C temperature. All samples were conditioned at the same standard atmospheric conditions for at least 24 hours prior to the measurements. Tensile properties were measured using an INSTRON 4301 apparatus, while the number of turns of twist was counted using a standard twist tester. For each sample ten specimens were tested and

the mean values of results used for data presentation (Table 1).

Measurement of creep

Creep was measured under two thermal loading conditions: isothermal and non-isothermal (cyclic). The test specimen were yarn, raw cord and dipped cord. The humidity change following a change in temperature was ignored. Samples were conditioned at standard atmospheric conditions for 24 hours prior to measurements. To ensure that testing times were reasonable to allow the completion of the study within the limited time, 60 % of breaking load of each sample was chosen as initial strain load.

Isothermal experiments

Creep behaviour of various samples was measured at room temperature (around 20 °C), 50 °C, 75 °C, 100 °C, 130 °C and 150 °C. For each experimental temperature, ten specimens per sample were tested. The temperature of the working chamber was first raised to the required level and the specimens were then loaded to the 60 % stress level (60 % of breaking load that was measured at standard atmospheric conditions). At 100 °C and above, each sample loading took a little over half a minute resulting in a fall of the actual chamber temperature by no more than 5 °C. It needed 2 to 3 minutes for the temperature to pick up to the required level. Below 100 °C the fall of the chamber temperature for the above reason was no more than 3 °C. The creep performance of the specimens as a function of time was recorded until they failed.

Non-isothermal (cyclic) experiments

For non-isothermal (cyclic) experiments, specimens were loaded inside the work-

Sample	Linear density(tex)	Twists/cm		Elongation at break(%)	Breaking force(N)	Tenacity (N/tex)
		plied	singles			
Yarn (210 filaments)	140	none		15.5	98.2	0.70
Raw Cord	313	3.2S*	3.1Z*	21.5	177.7	0.57
Dipped Cord	320	3.4S*	2.8Z*	21.6	176.6	0.55

S* and Z indicate the direction of twist

ing chamber at ambient temperature ($\approx 21^\circ\text{C}$). Following loading, the temperature was raised to a pre-set maximum level (150°C or 130°C or 100°C). For each cyclic temperature ten specimens per sample were tested. Once the temperature reached the pre-set maximum, a cooling operation began and the chamber temperature was brought back to about 25°C to complete one thermal cycle. The process was left to continue until the specimen failed. Creep performance of the specimens was recorded during the experiments.

For both isothermal and non-isothermal (cyclic) experiments, the average results for each group of ten specimens were taken for further analysis.

Results and discussion

Preliminary results on isothermal experiments conducted at room temperature, 50°C , 75°C , 100°C , 130°C , and 150°C on yarn, raw cord and dipped cord have shown that at 60% stress level, all specimens, irrespective of their geometry, exhibit an instantaneous elongation on loading followed by steady creeping over time, with an eventual failure (Fig. 2–4). According to Takeyama and Matsui [3], tyre cords behave in a similar manner under real life loading conditions, although they carry a maximum load of only up to 20% of their breaking load.

Results by Wilding and Ward [5, 6] on creep and recovery of ultra-high-modulus of polyethylene show a steady and continuous increase in creep with time,

which, suddenly accelerated as the specimen nears rupture, even at a low temperature of 20°C . In this study a similar trend of creep was observed. The creep rate however was much more reduced as compared to that observed by Wilding and Ward but increased with increasing temperature, leading to quick rupture at high temperatures. The results obtained at low temperatures are similar to those obtained by Leaderman [2] when he investigated the creep of nylon filaments under standard atmospheric conditions of temperature and humidity, although his investigation were short term as compared to those in this study.

The results in Fig. 2–4 show that increasing operating temperature accelerates creep rate, and significantly reduces creep failure time. It is envisaged that high operating temperature and level of stress can activate a large number of processes in a semicrystalline polymer like nylon6.6. Mukhopadhyay [7] states that at 100°C hydrogen bonds in nylon6.6 can be subjected to thermal vibrations and amorphous materials could be in a liquid like state of dynamic equilibrium. Application of uniaxial load to a nylon 6.6 yarn or cord at a reasonably high temperature (e.g. 100°C) will, therefore, cause a flow in the amorphous regions activating (i) rapid material extension, (ii) creation of more weak points, (iii) initiation of cracks and (iv) eventual failure.

Results from this study show that instantaneous extension for the yarn was just over 13% and that for raw cord and dipped cord was over 18%. The mathematical representation of creep

shows that the experimental curves are defined by an equation [8]:

$$e = e_0 + \text{creep} \quad (1)$$

where e_0 is the instantaneous extension,

$$\text{creep} = \sigma_0/E(1 - e^{-t/\tau}) \quad (2)$$

where σ_0 is initial stress, E is elastic modulus, t creep is time, τ is retardation time.

When $t = 0$, $e = e_0$, and when $t = \infty$ $e_\infty \approx e_r = e_0 + \sigma_0/E$,

$$\text{resulting in } \sigma_0/E = e_r - e_0 \quad (3)$$

where e_r is the strain at rupture.

Strains e_0 and σ_0/E , and retardation time τ are constant which means the total strain e is dependent on time t.

Results have also shown that both raw cord and dipped cord exhibit relatively high initial extensibility as compared to the yarn. Highly twisted structure of the cord is obviously responsible for that. However, Fig. 2–4 shows that the ultimate creep life of a cord is much shorter than a yarn. It is reasonable to assume that the filaments in a highly twisted and strained cord can promote high levels of frictional forces between themselves causing possible surface crack initiation [9]. As temperature increases, such cracks propagate very fast due to flow behaviour of polymeric chains resulting in faster failure.

Further analysis of the results has shown that the temperature-creep life relationship can be defined by an equation

Fig. 2. Creep-time relationships of raw cord and dipped cord at room temperature

Fig. 3. Creep-time relationships of yarn, raw cord and dipped cord at 75°C

Fig. 4. Creep-time relationships of yarn, raw cord and dipped cord at 150 °C

Fig. 5. Creep life-temperature relationships of yarn and cords at 60% stress level

Fig. 6. Creep-time relationships of yarn raw cord and dipped cord at temperatures cycling between around 25 °C and 150 °C

$y = ae^{bx}$, where y is the creep life and x is temperature, a and b are constants [9]. This is confirmed by plotting $\ln y$ against x (Fig. 5) which exhibits straight-line graphs. The values of a and b were calculated using the least squares method and are given in Table 2.

Results obtained from non-isothermal (cyclic) experiments indicate a similar pattern as in isothermal experiments. Both raw and dipped cords continue to exhibit relatively high initial extension as compared to the yarn. The yarn again shows longer life than the raw and the dipped cords. However, creep lives of all samples were much longer compared to the observations made on isothermal experiments. Specimens were also creeping more evenly and steadily irrespective of their cyclic temperature conditions (Fig. 6). Specimens creeping under cyclic mode of temperature environment (room to 150 °C) provided 5 to 7 times longer life than a similar specimen experienced at constant operating temperature of 150 °C. On the whole cyclic operating temperature mode (heating-cooling-heating and so on) always provided a much longer creep life to the specimen compared to the same specimen treated at steady state isothermal temperature mode.

Obviously at non-isothermal (cyclic) temperatures, the creep time before rupture was longer than at their corresponding isothermal temperatures because yarn and cord specimens go through different creep phases, for example when the cycle reaches a low temperature materials show little or no creep at all perhaps due to glassy nature of the polymer (nylon6.6) at about that temperature. These phases do not arise under isothermal operating mode. Thus the different creep phases experienced by the specimens during cyclic mode operations ultimately extend specimen lifetime compared to a similar specimen subjected to isothermal temperature of 150 °C or 130 °C or 100 °C.

The dipped cord exhibited the shortest creep life because according to Wake [10], treatment of cords with RFL resin is done at high temperature, which could have allowed the penetration of the RFL dope into the nylon cord structure, causing surface swelling disrupting the intramolecular hydrogen bonds and weakening the fibre structure. Although Wootton

Table 2: Equation Defining Temperature-creep life Relationships and their Coefficients of Determination R²

	Temperature-creep equation	R ²
Yarn	$y = 5.59 \times 10^4 e^{-0.061x}$	0.997
Raw cord	$y = 1.45 \times 10^4 e^{-0.054x}$	0.997
Dipped cord	$y = 1.25 \times 10^4 e^{-0.061x}$	0.993

Fig. 7. Possible reaction between RF resin and nylon6.6

[11] states that there is no entirely satisfactory chemical reaction between RFL and cords, he agrees that some reaction could take place between the hydroxyl (OH) and the amide(NH) (Fig. 7). This reaction disturbs the fibre molecular structure. As a result the cord becomes stiff, slightly brittle, and more susceptible to rupture.

Conclusion

Results obtained using the new apparatus at constant temperatures were comparable to those done by other researchers, which suggests that the designed apparatus operated within acceptable standards.

The creep rate of nylon6.6 tyre cords decreases with time but increases with an increase in operating temperature. The temperature of the testing environment coupled with stress not only influence the creep but the frictional forces between filaments within the twisted and strained cord, resulting in shorter creep life of a cord specimen as compared to that of the yarn.

The study revealed that when simulating the operating conditions of the tyre, by using non-isothermal conditions, the creep life of cords under such conditions significantly increased as compared to that at constant temperature. It is undoubtedly true from the modest data obtained that stops made during long journeys do not only cool down the engine of

the vehicle but the tyre as well giving an extended operating life.

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